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ALMA MATER STUDIORUM
UNIVERSITÀ DI BOLOGNA

Decarbonizing livestock structures: retrofit of a pig barn using renewable sources

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Introduction

- The study was developed within the innovation project RES4LIVE
“Energy Smart Livestock Farming towards Zero Fossil Fuel Consumption”
- Period 2020-2024
- Call “Defossilising agriculture – solutions and pathways for fossil-energy-free farming”
- European program Horizon 2020

www.res4live.eu

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No.101000785

Project Overview

Intensive Livestock Farming is one of the most **energy consuming** sub-sectors of agriculture, mainly based on fossil fuels use

Electricity and thermal energy is required to cover strongly diversified energy demand

More sustainable livestock production and de-fossilising energy needs in husbandry facilities emerge as **crucial aspects within EU**

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Project Overview

- **100% replacement of fossil energy in intensive livestock farming sector** utilizing Renewable Energy Sources (RES)
- A **combination of technologies and solutions** will be installed and evaluated in 4 livestock farms

Market integrated, cost-effective & case-sensitive RES solutions towards fossil-free livestock farming

OBJECTIVE

- Focus on Italian pilot case of swine farm
- De-fossilization project involving the nursery barn: development and installation of an integrated RES system combining
 - a photovoltaic-thermal plant,
 - a geothermal storage, and
 - a modular heat pump.
- A smart control system was also designed to be installed for indoor environment monitoring and energy management.

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PILOT CASE

- Via Falconiera, 35 – 41037 MIRANDOLA (MO) -Italy

- amministrazione@agricolagolinelli.it

GOLINELLI
AZIENDA AGRICOLA

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Pig farm

- 500 sows
- 2500 weaners
- A variable number of hogs

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Interventions

13. Gestation barn
NO INTERVENTIONS

12. Hog barn with gestation sector
THERMAL INSULATION OF THE ENVELOPE

17. Offices/dressing room
NO INTERVENTIONS

14. Farrowing barn
NO INTERVENTIONS

9, 10. Warehouses
NO INTERVENTIONS

15. Gestation barn
NO INTERVENTIONS

Geothermal storage with vertical boreholes

PVT system to provide electricity for heat pump and nursery barn, and thermal energy for underground heat storage

16. Nursery barn
Replacement of the LPG boiler with a 35 kW heat pump

DEFOSSILIZATION IN NURSERY BARN

Replacement of the LPG boiler with a 35 kW heat pump

Plan layout of nursery barn

Integrated RES system

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Realizing tailored geothermal probes

→ Tailored realization (10 and 30 m) starting from commercial 100 m probes

→ Borehole heat exchangers «Double U».

→ One «U» dedicated to the solar energy storage – circuit PVT

→ One «U» dedicated to the heat extraction – circuit HP

Creating the conditions for a long term monitoring

Two existing wells

25 m depth

50 m distance, downwards the BTES

Maximum flow: 4 l/s

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Installation and monitoring

Rotary drilling
No need of drilling bit
Only water as drilling fluid

Grouted boreholes
Pressure tests before
and after installation

Nonwoven geotextile
for piezometers
Movable and fixed temperature
and level monitoring

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Geological parameters

Depth	Stratigraphy	Hydraulic conductivity	Porosity	Thermal conductivity	Thermal diffusivity
0-10 m	Silt and clay	$10^{-10} - 10^{-9}$ m/s	0-5%	0.65 W/(m·K)	0.03 m ² /d
10-12 m	Sandy humps and clayey sands (aquitard)	$10^{-6} - 10^{-5}$ m/s	10-15%	1-2 W/(m·K)	0.07 m ² /d
12-50 m	Sand (aquifer, confined)	$10^{-5} - 10^{-4}$ m/s	30-40%	2-3 W/(m·K)	0.10 m ² /d
≈ 50 m	Clay and clayey sands	$10^{-6} - 10^{-5}$ m/s	5-10%	0.7-0.9 W/(m·K)	0.03 m ² /d
50-80 m	Sand (aquifer, confined)	$10^{-5} - 10^{-4}$ m/s	30-40%	2-3 W/(m·K)	0.10 m ² /d
80-100 m	Clay and clayey sands	$10^{-10} - 10^{-9}$ m/s	5-10%	0.7-0.9 W/(m·K)	0.03 m ² /d
> 100 m	Sand (aquifer, confined)	$10^{-5} - 10^{-3}$ m/s	30-40%	2-3 W/(m·K)	0.10 m ² /d

Thermal Response Test

- 1 BoreHole 10 m
- 1 BH 30 m
- 2 piezometers 25 m

Results TRT 10 m

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon programme.

Results TRT 30 m

This project has received funding from the European Union under the Marie Skłodé Curie Grant

Design preliminary tips – energy loads

	Ground energy extraction Circuit HP (kWh)	Solar energy storage Circuit PVT (kWh)
Jan	4503	904
Feb	4442	1043
Mar	1807	2490
Apr	810	2720
May	404	3842
Jun	11	3735
Jul	1	4756
Aug	1	3984
Sep	26	2859
Oct	1149	1905
Nov	2319	1013
Dec	3965	1005
TOTAL	19437	30256

Numerical model of geothermal storage

This project has received

Design of geothermal storage, depth 30m

Inlet line from PVT to BoreHole
Outlet line from BH to PVT
Inlet line from Heat Pump to BHol
Outlet line from HP to BH

PERFORMANCE OF THE DESIGNED SYSTEM

	Heat Source temperature °C		Heat Pump COP
	Water	Air	
<i>Only Heat Pump</i>	-	1	2.5
	0	6	2.8
	5	11	3.0
	10	16	3.4
<i>Heat Pump + Geothermal Storage</i>	15	21	3.9
	20	26	4.5
	25	31	5.0

CONCLUSIONS

- The solutions developed have been applied in the design and installation phase to optimize the integration of PVT, Borehole Thermal Energy Storage (BTES) and Dual Source Heat Pump (DSHP).
- The results demonstrate that the energy demand of a livestock farm can be met by a mix of RES properly defined, specifically designed to optimally exploit the renewable resources typically available in farming environments.

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